

IMPROVING THE COMPUTATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPACT SIMULATIONS ON WOVEN FRP COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates several strategies to improve the computational efficiency of numerical simulations aimed at predicting impact damage in woven fibre reinforced composites. Utilisation of homogenised ply-scale modelling, performed using a VUMAT user-defined material model, was justified for plain weave woven laminates. The commercial finite element software Abaqus/Explicit was used for progressive damage modelling in woven carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminates. Along stress-based failure initiation criteria and energy-driven damage evolution, complete loss of load-bearing capability is captured by effective failure strain-based element removal, thus enabling the accurate assessment of full perforation energy margin. Validation of the numerical model was performed through impact simulations at two energy levels in which steel spherical impactors induce damage in composite plates made of plain weave CFRP with the layup [45, 0, 45, 0, 45]_s. The results have shown that in this study the homogenised approach has performed well, and that careful implementation of simplifications in the model leads to significant improvement in computational efficiency while retaining the accuracy level. Namely, a remarkable total time reduction of over 75 % was achieved from initial model. Thus, the final model is rendered much more suitable for practical, industrial purposes in which large structural components are examined.

1 INTRODUCTION

Utilization of composite materials in aeronautical, automotive, military and other major industry segments is well established. Due to many advantages, such as more balanced properties, enhanced impact resistance and improved ease of handling [1], woven carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites are seeing continuous increase in utilization in important structural elements. However, based on the available references, it can be concluded that woven CFRP materials are significantly less investigated compared to their unidirectional (UD) CFRP counterparts [2]. Thus, the uncertainties concerning the assumptions and simplifications introduced in modelling that are still existent even regarding the UD composites, are projected to the woven composites as well, and are perhaps even more pronounced.

Research studies focused on woven CFRP are usually performed at the microscale, e.g. [3], due to their complex microstructure. The microstructural geometry of these materials consists of interlaced and interconnected fibre bundles in warp and weft directions, potential voids, resin pockets or resin-rich zones and interfaces between fabric bundles and matrix. For the same reasons, micromechanical modelling of woven composites is significantly more challenging than that of UD composites [2]. The microscale approach enables capturing the behaviour of the micro-geometrical features of the woven material in the most accurate manner. However, this capability is accompanied with an enormous computational cost, deeming the micromechanical approach inapplicable for engineering problems. In

the microscale modelling approach, a single unit cell that would be represented by a single finite element in the homogenised approach, is discretized using many finite elements with explicit contact interactions between them. This level of detail dramatically increases the computational cost compared to the homogenised ply-scale approach.

However, despite capturing many microscopic features of woven fabrics, these detailed models still rely on certain assumptions and are subject to uncertainties—particularly concerning void content and the simplified representation of bonding between individual fibres and the matrix, as well as between fibre bundles and the matrix [2]. Additionally, the need to impose idealised boundary conditions introduces further sources of uncertainty in the analysis.

Multiscale methods enable application of micromechanical approaches in the engineering applications. However, these models contain algorithms that analyse the material at various scales and are thus even more complex. Furthermore, multiscale models for woven composites require calculations on some of the analysed regions to be performed multiple times, i.e., at different scales. Consequently, although multiscale approaches offer improved computational efficiency compared to microscale models, they are still too computationally demanding for engineering applications. This is particularly the case in transient dynamic analyses, where explicit finite element simulations require extremely small time increments.

In contrast, well-defined ply-level homogenisation approaches can simplify complex numerical simulations, offering considerably increased computational efficiency. The selection of the material segment used to construct a homogenised volume element (referred to as HVE in this work) can vary based on its size and location, allowing flexibility for different woven fabric architectures. The HVE strategy proposed in this work is based on the experimentally determined properties of woven composites. As the internal geometry of the fabric is not considered explicitly, the need for specifically defined boundary conditions is eliminated. Instead, the approach assumes that the finite element boundaries align with the interlacing regions of the woven fabric. The HVE discretisation approach is explained visually in Fig. 1. As shown, the possible HVEs in woven composites differ by the boundary conditions corresponding to neighbouring fibre bundle interlacings causing variances in stiffness and strengths. In finite element modelling, this variety can be reduced by limiting the average in-plane size of the finite elements employed to the width of a single fibre bundle or, alternatively, to a specified natural number of fibre bundles. Figure 1 presents the Plain Weave, 2x2 Twill and 4H Satin weave fabrics with various HVEs obtained by identifying different 1 x 1 (blue squares) and 2 x 2 (magenta squares) fibre bundle elements. For the clarity of the display, not all existing variants of 2 x 2 HVEs were marked on Figure 1 for the Twill and Harness Satin weaves.

Figure 1. Various possible homogenised volume elements (HVEs) for Plain weave, 2x2 Twill weave and 4 Harness Satin weave woven fabrics: 1 x 1 (blue) and 2 x 2 (magenta) fibre bundle sized HVEs

By increasing the HVE dimensions, the numerical problems are simplified as the microstructural geometry is more homogeneous and the overall number of degrees of freedom is reduced. However, a compromise between accuracy and computational efficiency has to be made to simulate engineering problems. Even in the case of utilization of the smallest HVE (1 x 1 fibre bundle size), the computational efficiency of homogenized approaches is still superior compared to the micromechanical or multiscale approaches.

Despite having the most interlacings and thus potentially the highest quantities of resin-rich zones, resin pockets and voids – all of which reduce their strength, Plain weave fabrics have the most balanced properties when considering the HVEs of the material. Moreover, with the correct size of the homogenised finite element modelling, plain weave fabrics are the only fabric type that can be discretised by only a single variant of HVE. This is shown in Figure 1, in which for the Plain weave fabric two of all of the HVE sizes (1 x 1 and 2 x 2) are marked. However, their boundary conditions, number and position of interlacings in these sets of two HVEs are the same, hence rendering the same properties, with the assumption that warp and weft fibre bundles are equal.

Furthermore, various positions of the, e.g., 3 x 3 HVEs are obtainable. Of all of the possible HVEs in the Plain weave fabric, the only ideally balanced and homogenised, i.e. presumably orthotropic, are the ones that are perfectly cut along the fibre bundle boundaries and the ones cut exactly in the middle of warp and weft fibre bundles.

Clearly, it is impractical to try to fit the HVEs discretising the model to correspond to the exact positions of the fibre bundles in the real structure to be modelled. However, it is evident that the largest error, i.e., discrepancy, in the position between the utilized HVE and the closest one of the ideal cases is half of the width of the fibre bundle. Moreover, the larger the HVE, the less significant this error is. For example, for a 2 x 2 HVE, the maximum error in position is 25 % of the length of the homogenised element, whereas for the 5 x 5 HVE, the error is 10 % of the length of the homogenised element. Despite the large percentage of these errors defined in this manner, it is evident that it is practically negligible considering the overall length of the structure. For example, for a structure with a 100 mm length in the examined direction, considering a 1 mm fibre bundle width, for any chosen size of the HVE, this error in the shifting of the position of the HVEs is, at maximum, only 0.5 %.

In this study, the homogenised ply-scale approach is utilized, mainly for computational efficiency, as it is by far the most efficient approach and the only practical solution for applications in explicit dynamic analyses as elaborated previously. In the light of the aforementioned problems with homogenised ply-level discretization of woven fabric plies, to reduce uncertainties and retain physical meaningfulness of the model, application of this model is restricted to plain-weave woven fabric plies. Furthermore, the in-plane dimensions of the finite elements modelling the woven fabric composite structures are defined by and restricted to the width of the fibre bundles, thus rendering the approximately 1 x 1 x 0.21 mm solid finite elements.

2 METHODOLOGY

The material behaviour is assumed to be elastic orthotropic prior to any damage initiation. Additionally, for all three shear modes, a non-linear behaviour is modelled. Because of the assumed orthotropy of the material, shear behaviour is decoupled from normal behaviour, simplifying the implementation of shear non-linearity.

2.1 Shear Non-Linearity

Non-linearity is especially pronounced in the shear response of woven composites. This nonlinear behaviour is introduced according to the stress to strain relation proposed by Coles et al. [4]:

$$\tau_{ij} = S_{ij} \cdot \left[1 - \exp \left\{ -\frac{G_{ij}^0 \cdot \gamma_{ij}}{S_{ij}} \right\} \right], \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, i \neq j. \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), S_{ij} is the shear strength, G_{ij}^0 is the shear modulus and γ_{ij} is the instantaneous engineering shear strain. The shear stress vs. shear strain plot obtained by the non-linear formulation provided in Eq. (1) for the values of shear strength $S_{ij} = 100$ MPa and shear modulus $G_{ij}^0 = 4$ GPa respectively, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Non-linear shear behaviour: stress-strain plot

2.2 Failure criteria

The in-plane failure initiation corresponding to fibre rupture is modelled using the interactive stress criteria adopted from the study [4] for warp (FF1) and weft (FF2) direction in tensile (T) and compressive (C) loading conditions:

$$FF1T = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \quad (2)$$

$$FF1C = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \quad (3)$$

$$FF2T = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \text{ and} \quad (4)$$

$$FF2C = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1. \quad (5)$$

In Eqs. (2) - (5), σ_{11} , σ_{22} , τ_{12} , τ_{13} and τ_{23} are the stress components, whereas X_t , X_c , Y_t , Y_c are the warp and weft tensile and compressive strengths, respectively, while S_{12} , S_{13} and S_{23} are the shear strengths of the material.

Matrix micro-cracks forming and coalescing into larger cracks is exhibited by shear non-linear material behaviour, according to e.g. [5, 6]. Interactive quadratic stress criteria are used for evaluating intralaminar matrix tensile (MFT) and compressive (MFC) damage initiation. Matrix failure is defined using the through-thickness normal and all three shear stress components, while the failure mode is predicted based on the sign of the through-thickness stress:

$$MFT = \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \quad (6)$$

$$MFC = \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1. \quad (7)$$

2.3 Progressive Damage Evolution

Progressive damage evolution is modelled by the degradation of material stiffness through modification of the stiffness matrix. The damage variable d can be considered as an internal parameter describing the reduction of the load bearing material surface from the undamaged state to the current, instantaneous state, as proposed in the early studies by Murakami [7], Matzenmiller et al. [8] and Zako et al. [9]. The stress reduction related to material damage can be described by the following simplified general relation:

$$\sigma = (1 - d) \cdot \sigma' = (1 - d) \cdot \mathbf{C} \varepsilon = \mathbf{C}_d \varepsilon, \quad (8)$$

in which σ' is the nominal, undamaged stress vector determined by the Hooke's law from the undamaged stiffness matrix \mathbf{C} and strain vector ε while assuming the orthotropic linear elasticity of the material. In

Eq. (8), the damaged stiffness matrix \mathbf{C}_d has been introduced by combining the damage vector d consisting of warp direction d_{f1} and weft direction d_{f2} damage variable with the undamaged stiffness matrix \mathbf{C} . This can be expanded for the first three, i.e., normal, coupled components as:

$$\mathbf{C}_d^N = \frac{1}{\Delta} \begin{bmatrix} d_{f1}E_{11}(1 - d_{f2}v_{23}v_{32}) & d_{f1}d_{f2}E_{11}(v_{21} + v_{23}v_{31}) & d_{f1}E_{11}(v_{31} + d_{f2}v_{21}v_{32}) \\ d_{f1}d_{f2}E_{11}(v_{12} + v_{32}v_{13}) & d_{f2}E_{22}(1 - d_{f1}v_{13}v_{31}) & d_{f2}E_{22}(v_{32} + d_{f1}v_{12}v_{31}) \\ d_{f1}E_{11}(v_{13} + d_{f2}v_{12}v_{23}) & d_{f2}E_{22}(v_{23} + d_{f1}v_{21}v_{13}) & E_{33}(1 - d_{f1}d_{f2}v_{12}v_{21}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Damage in the shear components is modelled as:

$$\mathbf{C}_d^S = \frac{1}{\Delta} \begin{bmatrix} d_{f1}d_{f2}G_{12}^0\Delta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d_{f2}G_{23}^0\Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_{f1}G_{31}^0\Delta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

When damage is initiated, the initial, intact shear moduli G_{ij}^0 in the Eq. (1), should be replaced by the corresponding damaged stiffness matrix components introduced in Eq. (10). In the above equations, the remaining unintroduced variables are:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= 1 - d_{f1}d_{f2}v_{12}v_{21} - d_{f2}v_{23}v_{32} - d_{f1}v_{13}v_{31} - 2d_{f1}d_{f2}v_{12}v_{21}v_{21}, \\ d_{f1} &= (1 - d_{11}^t)(1 - d_{11}^c), \text{ and} \\ d_{f2} &= (1 - d_{22}^t)(1 - d_{22}^c). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The parameters $d_{ii}^{t/c}$ in Eq. (11) are the four different damage variables. These variables, corresponding to fibre tensile and compressive (upper index t/c) damage in warp and weft directions (lower index ii) are calculated according to, e.g., [10], by the relation:

$$d_{ii}^{t/c} = \frac{\varepsilon_{ii}^f \cdot (\varepsilon_{ii} - \varepsilon_{ii}^0)}{\varepsilon_{ii} \cdot (\varepsilon_{ii}^f - \varepsilon_{ii}^0)}. \quad (12)$$

In Eq. (12), ε_{ii}^0 is the corresponding equivalent strain at failure initiation, ε_{ii} is the instantaneous equivalent strain value, while ε_{ii}^f is the strain value of total rupture. The total rupture strain is determined depending on the corresponding fracture energy Γ_{ii} , corresponding equivalent stress at the point of failure initiation according to the failure initiation criteria in Eqs. (2) – (5), σ_{eq} , and the characteristic finite element length as: $\varepsilon_{ii}^f = 2 \cdot \Gamma_{ii} / (\sigma_{eq} \cdot L_c)$. The characteristic finite element length is introduced to ensure mesh-objectivity in the strain softening constitutive behaviour.

The presented formulation is a modification and a combination of the approaches presented by Hu et al. [11] and Coles et al. in [4] that represents a reasonable and physically sound approach to the modelling of the materials stiffness degradation.

Element deletion due to damage is employed in certain specific conditions. A total loss of load bearing capability is considered to occur only if fibre laid in both in-plane directions (warp and weft) have undergone total rupture. Thus, the finite element is removed when either tensile or compressive damage variables in both warp ($d_{11}^{t/c}$) and weft ($d_{22}^{t/c}$) directions reach their maximum defined value, which is chosen to be 0.98 to avoid numerical problems associated with excessive distortion of degraded finite elements.

Furthermore, to prevent large distortions and unphysical deformations of degraded finite elements, as well as to capture the matrix failure, along with enabling the accurate simulation of perforation behaviour of the laminated structures, the effective failure strain (EFS) element removal criterion is implemented. This criterion is defined as:

$$\varepsilon_{eff} \leq \varepsilon_{eff}^{\max}, \quad (13)$$

where ε_{eff}^{\max} is the semi-empirical material parameter, defining the maximum effective strain that a material point, i.e. single finite element with reduced integration could sustain, above which complete

material failure is expected. In the Eq. (13), effective strain ε_{eff} is calculated based on the deviatoric strain components e_{ij} as:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{2 \cdot e_{ij}^2 / 3}. \quad (14)$$

The maximum effective strain $\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{max}}$ is taken to be 0.3 in this study. This value is in similar to the values employed by other researchers, such as in [12], when using similar failure strain element removal criteria.

2.4 Interlaminar behaviour

Zero-thickness cohesive finite elements (COH3D8) were used to model the ply interfaces. To capture delamination phenomena, the Abaqus built-in decoupled traction-separation cohesive material model was used in this study. The model employs quadratic traction failure initiation criterion, and the B-K energy driven delamination propagation, with the B-K factor set to $\eta = 2$. Furthermore, the interface stiffness parameters were estimated according to the relationship suggested in [13]: $K_{nn} = E_{33}/h_0$, $K_{ss} = G_{13}/h_0$ and $K_{tt} = G_{23}/h_0$, where E_{33} , G_{13} and G_{23} are the matrix material elastic properties, and h_0 is the assumed thickness of the interface. As proposed in [13, 14] the interface thickness h_0 can be taken as 1/10 of the thickness of the ply.

Cohesive element removal was set when the damage variable reaches the value of 0.98 for stability reasons.

3 NUMERICAL MODEL

Numerical simulations of the impact experiments in [14] have been used in this study to validate the model. Thus, a 12.7 mm diameter spherical steel impactor with the total falling mass of the drop weight apparatus equal to 1.573 kg was simulated to impact the plain weave woven CFRP plates. Simulations of two impact energies (16 J and 28 J) were performed.

Several FE modelling strategies were investigated. The rectangular plate with the dimensions 100 x 150 mm has been modelled with solid (C3D8R) elements in Abaqus. The layup is $[45, 0, 45, 0, 45]_s$ layup, resulting in the 2.1 mm total thickness. A single finite element has been employed in the thickness direction for each composite ply. Thus the numerical model consists of a total of 150,000 C3D8R finite elements. At all interfaces of the composite plies a total of 135,000 zero-thickness cohesive COH3D8 finite elements were utilized for delamination modelling. Results obtained using this modelling strategy are further denoted as “Full” simulation results.

The plate is simply supported along all edges at its backside. The steel impactor was modelled as a discretely rigid body, and all of its degrees of freedom were constrained, except for the vertical movement. General contact algorithm was employed with hard normal and tangential contact with a defined penalty frictional coefficient of 0.3. The model is schematically represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Numerical model with boundary conditions and loading

The mechanical intralaminar and interlaminar properties were taken from [14], and the already mentioned related study [13] of the same research group. All of the necessary intralaminar stiffness constants, strengths and fracture energies are listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 1. Intralaminar elastic properties of the plain weave CFRP ply

property	E_1	E_2	E_3	G_{12}	$G_{13} = G_{23}$	ν_{12}	$\nu_{13} = \nu_{23}$
unit	[GPa]	[GPa]	[GPa]	[GPa]	[GPa]	[-]	[-]
reference	[14]	[14]	[14]	[14]	[13]	[14]	[4]*
value	60.8	58.25	2.97	4.55	1.08	0.07	0.35

* Value calculated based on the value in [4], according to the ratio of η_{12} values from [14] and [4]

Table 2. Intralaminar strengths of the plain weave CFRP ply, taken from [14]

property	X_t	X_c	Y_t	Y_c	S_{12}	$S_{13} = S_{23}$
unit	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]
value	621	760	594	707	125	150

Table 3. Intralaminar fracture energies of the plain weave CFRP ply, taken from [14]

property	G_{ft}	G_{fc}	G_{mt}	G_{mc}	G_{sh}
unit	[kJ/m ²]				
value	75	25	2.5	2.5	2.25

The interlaminar fictitious penalty stiffness constants are $K_I = 141430 \text{ N/mm}^3$, $K_{II} = 216670 \text{ N/mm}^3$ and $K_{III} = 514290 \text{ N/mm}^3$, based on the values of shear moduli reported in [13]. The remaining interlaminar model properties are taken directly from [14] and are as follows: $N = 75 \text{ MPa}$, $S_{II} = 125 \text{ MPa}$, $S_{III} = 150 \text{ MPa}$, $G_I = 0.6 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, $G_{II} = 5.5 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, $G_{III} = 5.5 \text{ kJ/m}^2$.

To investigate the effect of the employed cohesive elements on the computational efficiency, a modelling strategy without cohesive elements at the ply interfaces was performed. Consequently, this model consists only of the solid finite elements of the composite plies, without the ability to simulate the delamination failure mode. The results obtained by this simulation type are remarked as the “Bulk” simulation results.

The next modelling strategy consists of a hybrid approach that was tested for increasing the computational efficiency while retaining the capability to accurately assess both intralaminar and interlaminar damage. In this model, the VUMAT user-defined material is employed only on the central 50 x 50 mm part of the composite plate, whereas on the remaining, outer portion of the plate, the Abaqus built-in orthotropic material with the same elastic properties was employed. Furthermore, the cohesive interface model with zero-thickness cohesive finite elements was included only on the central 50 x 50 mm portion of the plate as well. Hence, the outer part of the plate is incapable of assessing any failure and damage mode. This model is in the Results section denoted as “Hybrid” simulation model and results.

Figure 4 schematically presents the employed meshing strategy in the transition zone from the outer composite plate area (Abaqus built-in orthotropic material model without damage) to the inner area of specific interest (VUMAT material model + cohesive zone for delamination) for impact analyses.

Figure 4. Meshing strategy in the transition zone from outer to inner plate area

All simulations were performed on a desktop workstation using 22 2.2 GHz processors. The details on the finite element meshes for the three simulation modelling approaches are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Details of the finite element meshes for different modelling approaches

	“Full”	“Bulk”	“Hybrid”
Total number of nodes, [-]	305,020	167,761	191,170
Total number of elements, [-]	285,000	150,000	172,500
VUMAT elements, [-]	150,000	150,000	25,000
Cohesive elements, [-]	135,000	0	22,500

4 RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the comparison of numerical to experimental impactor displacement history and contact force history for the impact energy of 16 J. Both graphs contain results obtained by employing the presented three modelling approaches, namely: “Full”, “Bulk” and “Hybrid”.

Figure 5. Comparison of numerical to experimental results [14] for the 16 J impact: contact force and impactor displacement

The results in Figure 5 indicate that, overall, the simulation results correspond well with the experimental data in both plots. A more pronounced difference is observed in the contact force history, where all three models similarly overestimate its magnitude. This tendency to overpredict the contact force may be related to an underestimation of the plate’s final absorbed energy and additional investigation will have to be performed to identify the source. Additionally, the lower predicted absorbed energy could result from insufficient estimation of interlaminar damage, which will be examined in the continuation of this work. The overall slope of the numerical curves matches the experimental curve slope reasonably well. The contact force history graph shows that the “Bulk” simulation results align more closely with the experimental data. Contrarily, the simulations incorporating cohesive elements

(“Full” and “Hybrid” models) show oscillatory behaviour. Additionally, the oscillation frequency is higher in the “Hybrid” simulation. This is likely related to the smaller area covered by cohesive elements in that case, which reduces the time needed for stress waves to reflect from the boundaries of the delamination modelling region. Figure 6 shows a comparison between experimental and numerical delamination areas for the two investigated impact energies. The red outlines (profiles) were derived from C-scan images presented in [14], while the orange and blue regions indicate the areas where cohesive elements were completely removed in the “Full” and “Hybrid” simulations. In the lower part of the figure, the green and purple regions correspond to solid intralaminar elements exhibiting tensile or compressive matrix damage in the “Full” and “Hybrid” models.

Figure 6. Comparisons of “Full” and “Hybrid” simulations’ numerically and experimentally [14] obtained delamination areas for impacts of 16 J and 28 J

Figure 6 shows that the simulated delamination areas are smaller compared to the experimental results. Furthermore, the comparison indicates that including elements with matrix damage (tensile or compressive) leads to a better match with experimental results. As discussed in [15] and [16], increasing load causes matrix micro-cracks to merge into larger intralaminar cracks. When such a crack extends to the ply boundaries (interfaces between the plies) it leads to initiation and growth of delamination, explaining the motivation for the comparison presented in Figure 6. From the perspective of the experimental findings in the existing studies such as [15, 16] and their confirmation from Figure 6, it seems that the phenomenological approach of connecting the interlaminar damage initiation to the propagation of intralaminar matrix damage in the adjacent plies could lead to improved overall delamination extent predictions. This is one of the main objectives of the authors’ current effort to develop a joint, combined VUMAT for both intralaminar and interlaminar composite progressive damage modelling.

For the computationally efficient “Hybrid” simulation, the discrepancy between numerical and experimental area in Figure 6 is barely larger than the one found in the comprehensive “Full” simulation model in which both intralaminar and interlaminar damage assessment is available for the whole volume of the composite plate. For the 16 J and 28 J impact cases, the “Hybrid” simulations’ results predict slightly lower extent of interlaminar damage compared to the “Full” simulations.

Finally, Table 5 summarizes the computational times for both investigated impact energy levels using all three simulation models, along with the corresponding percentages in reduction.

Table 5. Summary of all computational times - all three simulation strategies employed at both impact energies

	Time analysed, [ms]	“Full”, [min]	“Bulk”, [min]	Reduction from “Full”, [%]	“Hybrid”, [min]	Reduction from “Full”, [%]
16 J	7	2893	424	85.34	604	79.12
28 J	4	1882	404	78.53	410	78.21

From Table 5, it is clear that a significant increase in computational efficiency is achieved by both strategies: I) removing the interlaminar damage modelling from the model in “Bulk” simulations and II) reducing the zone of interest of the composite plate in which both intralaminar and interlaminar damage evaluation is available only to the central region of the composite plate in “Hybrid” simulations. It is visible that the reduction of computational time is constant in the case of “Hybrid” simulations.

On the other hand, different time savings were achieved by employing the “Bulk” simulations. These differences are attributed to different numbers of semi-detached cohesive finite elements which do not constructively contribute to the analysis model but deteriorate the stable time increment (STI). These highly distorted elements are a byproduct of removal of adjacent intralaminar solid elements of the plies above and below the interface. Because some of their nodes are free-floating, these semi-detached elements do not bear any load and thus could not be effectively removed from the simulation by reaching the maximum defined load driven, i.e., displacement driven damage variable value. The number of semi-detached cohesive finite elements is a function of, among other factors, the intensity of loading conditions and subsequent rate of removal of adjacent intralaminar solid finite elements.

Hence, it is expected that further improvements in the computational efficiency could be achieved by effectively removing any semi-detached cohesive elements from the simulation. This is another objective of the aforementioned key future agenda goal – development of the joint VUMAT user-defined material that is constituted of both intralaminar and interlaminar progressive damage material models.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, several FE modelling strategies have been investigated in the impact damage simulations in woven CFRP structures. Validation of the numerical model and the investigated modelling strategies was performed using experimental results of impact damage. The investigation is focused on plain weave woven architectures.

The numerical results overall demonstrated good agreement with experimental data for the simulated impact energies. Application of the VUMAT material model and interlaminar damage modelling to the central interior region of the plate (“Hybrid” simulations), it was possible to maintain satisfactory accuracy of the simulations at significantly lower computational time. However, this approach requires careful application, particularly regarding the accurate definition of the zone of interest or the anticipated damage region. A preliminary, faster simulation without interface modelling, e.g. using the “Bulk” simulations used in this work, can help identifying the likely extent of intralaminar damage before performing the detailed analysis.

The presented results are part of an ongoing investigation aimed at developing accurate numerical models for impact simulations in engineering problems. As stated throughout the Results section, future work will be focused on integrating the user-defined material behaviour of the plies and ply interfaces into a single VUMAT subroutine, which is considered to be a direction for further improvements in both accuracy and computational efficiency. Furthermore, as the constitutive model of the cohesive models will be user-defined, strain rate effects will be included in the subsequent models to additionally improve accuracy in the impact damage prediction.

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